

Report on Multiplier Event 7 (E7)

Event: Piliečių mokslas bibliotekininkams: atvirosios prieigos išteklių mokymo(si) perspektyvoje (Citizen Science for Librarians: open access resources from a teaching/learning perspective)

Date: 24.05.2024

Platform: MS Teams

Language: Lithuanian

Target group: Lithuanian academic and public library staff

Attendance: 272

Objectives of the event:

1. present the open access collection of resources on citizen science (PR6A1)
2. to present Citizen Science toolkit for Librarians (PR6A2) and its potential or use in teaching and learning
3. to demonstrate all the project results on Zenodo platform

Schedule: 14.00–15.00

1. LibOCS projekto pristatymas / Short presentation of LibOCS project (Giedrė Sabaitytė)
2. Kas yra piliečių mokslas? / What is citizen science? (Giedrė Sabaitytė and Laima Bucevičiūtė)
3. Projekto rezultatų aptarimas / Discussion of the project results (Giedrė Sabaitytė and Laima Bucevičiūtė)
 - a. Studijos „Transformuojantis universitetų bibliotekų ir kitų atminties institucijų vaidmuo atvirajame ir piliečių moksle Baltijos šalyse“ pristatymas / Presentation of a study “The Transformative Role of University Libraries and other Memory Institutions for Citizen Science and Open Science in the Baltics” (Giedrė Sabaitytė)
 - b. Interaktyvaus mokymosi kurso „LibOCS Piliečių mokslas bibliotekininkams: savarankiško mokymosi kursas“ pristatymas / Presentation of the interactive learning course "LibOCS Citizen Science for Librarians: a self-learning course" (Giedrė Sabaitytė)
 - c. Instituciniai pokyčiai ir BESPOC kontaktinio centro perspektyvos / Institutional changes and prospects for the BESPOC Contact Point (Laima Bucevičiūtė)
4. Atvirosios prieigos priemonių rinkinys / Citizen Science toolkit for Librarians (Laima Bucevičiūtė)
5. Atvirosios prieigos išteklių bibliotekininkams piliečių mokslo tema / Open access collection of resources for librarians on citizen science (Giedrė Sabaitytė)
6. Klausimai ir diskusijos / Questions and discussions

Marketing and communication

The invitations with a link to the registration form initially were distributed via Vytautas Magnus University Library website and Facebook account. It was also sent to the associated

partners of the project – Kaunas County Public Library (“Ažuolynas” Library) and Vilnius County Adam Mickiewicz Public Library. The invitation was also distributed via the Lithuanian Research Library Consortium mailing list.

Summary and reflections

Multiplier Event #7, milestone #39 of the LibOCS project, took place on 24th May 2024 as a virtual event in MS Teams platform. It was organised by Vytautas Magnus University Library.

The aim of the multiplier event was to present the possibilities of citizen science in libraries, to demonstrate the open access citizen science resource toolkit developed within the project "University libraries strengthening the academia-society connection through citizen science in the Baltics- LibOCS" and its potential for use in the teaching/learning perspective. It was primarily aimed at academic and public library staff, but was open for anyone interested in open and citizen science.

Topics covered in the webinar were the concept of citizen science, the role of libraries in the dissemination of citizen science ideas. The audience was introduced to the LibOCS project, and its results: a report “Drivers and barriers of citizen engagement in open science and the role of university libraries in the Baltics” (PR1A5), synthesis of the report in Lithuanian (PR1A6), study “The transformative role of university libraries for citizen and open science in the Baltics” (PR2A4), self-paced e-course for librarians (PR3A3), the process of BESPOC solutions implementation (PR5A3), citizen science toolkit (PR6A2), 100+ curated citizen science resources (PR6A1).

We started the event with an interactive activity to better know the audience. We presented participants with a poll asking them what they know about citizen science. The poll was answered by 83 respondents, 19% of whom were new to the term "citizen science", 48% admitted to having little knowledge of citizen science and only 3% said they were involved in citizen science activities. The survey confirmed that citizen science is a fairly new and relevant topic in the activities of Lithuanian libraries.

The workshop started with a brief overview of the concept of citizen science and a presentation of the project. This was followed by an overview of the project's achievements. Report “Drivers and barriers of citizen engagement in open science and the role of university libraries in the Baltics” and its Lithuanian synthesis “Piliečių įsitraukimo į atvirąjį mokslą varomosios jėgos ir kliūtys bei universitetų bibliotekų vaidmuo Baltijos šalyse” were introduced. The audience was briefed on the main guidelines of the report. The study "The Transformative Role of University Libraries and other Memory Institutions for Citizen Science and Open Science in the Baltics" was also presented, as well as a summary of the study in Lithuanian „Transformuojantis universitetų bibliotekų ir kitų atminties institucijų vaidmuo atvirajame ir piliečių moksle Baltijos šalyse“. A short demonstration of the interactive open access learning course for librarians "LibOCS Citizen Science for Librarians: a self-pace course". Later institutional changes and prospects for the BESPOC Contact Point in higher education institutions were presented. The second part of the seminar was dedicated to the toolkit. The audience had the opportunity to learn about the purpose, components, design and use of the toolkit. Later the list of the resources covered in the toolkit were presented. Next the collection of the project output in Zenodo was demonstrated.

272 participants (out of 416 registered) took part in the webinar. The participants were from 46 institutions (public and academic libraries, research institutes, Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Lithuania).

Feedback from the participants

After the event all registered participants were asked to give feedback on the event via a Google feedback form. Respondents were asked if the webinar was useful and whether they would use the material of webinar in their work or other activities. The respondents could also leave a general comment or suggestions.

We received 31 responses, 25 of them said that the webinar was very useful or rather useful. Overall, the webinar was assessed positively. Some were not sure, if they would use the material in their work.

Materials and recording

Slides and the recording of the webinar were uploaded in Zenodo collection.

Screenshots

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Citizen Science Toolkit for Librarians

About the Toolkit

Welcome to the Citizen Science toolkit for Librarians, an open access resource collection created collaboratively by five partners in the Erasmus+ project LIBOCS: University Libraries Strengthening the Academia-Society Connection through Citizen Science in the Baltics.

Contents:

- About the toolkit
- The Basics of Citizen Science
- Implementing Citizen Science in Libraries
- Citizen Science Portals
- Implementing Citizen Science Support Hub
- Citizen Scientists and Volunteers
- Training for Librarians
- Guides and Toolkits
- Information

The toolkit is designed for librarians interested in citizen science. The material was collected and stored throughout the project in the Zenodo LIBOCS

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Giedrė Sabaitytė Natalija Kežun

Sauga daiva jociene

Giedrė Sabaitytė

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Ovidijus ...

LIVE Poll: Names not recorded ; Results shared

Ką žinote apie piliečių mokslą

- Pirmą kartą apie tai girdžiu
- Kažką esu girdėjęs(-usi), bet nesu tikra(s)
- Žinau, kas yra piliečių mokslas
- Žinau ir dalyvauju piliečių mokslo veiklose

Submit Vote

Redaguota

Pirmą kartą apie tai girdžiu	19% (16)
Kažką esu girdėjęs(-usi), bet nesu tikra(s)	48% (40)
Žinau, kas yra piliečių mokslas	28% (24)
Žinau ir dalyvauju piliečių mokslo veiklose	3% (3)

83 responses